

Wearable Haptics for Interaction in Immersive VR in Children Neurorehabilitation

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Abstract—Immersive Virtual Reality has been investigated as an alternative and promising scenario to propose rehabilitation exercises to patients, with advantages in terms of flexibility and parametrization of the exercises, repeatability, and engagement. Modern, immersive VR systems provide novel features that are precious for usability of rehabilitation serious games in the clinical practice, envisaging also home-care applications. Still, the most of these impressive visual and audio virtual settings lack of the sense of touch: considering neurorehabilitation motor tasks, involving manipulation, the presence of haptic feedback is a key feature. We present here how haptic feedback can be introduced within an immersive serious game scenario, developed for rehabilitation of children with cerebral palsy. In the development, we considered different aspects including design of novel, highly wearable haptic devices, planning of the virtual rehabilitation exercise, and development of a dedicated haptic rendering strategy to provide an informative feedback during task execution.

Index Terms—haptic, rehabilitation, virtual, serious games, cerebral palsy, immersive, wearable

I. INTRODUCTION

Immersive Virtual Reality (VR) systems have seen an impressive progress in the last years regarding quality of the rendering, smooth head tracking, including also advanced characteristics that considerably improve usability and comfort of the user: wireless stand alone operation, fast donning and calibration of the system, and embedded hand tracking. The latter is a key feature for VR applications that include manipulation: the HMD alone becomes now enabled for bare-hands, immersive manipulation task without the need of any additional systems.

In neurorehabilitation, VR systems have been proposed and experimented in the shape of serious-games, combining engagement of the user with task oriented motor exercises [3]. Virtualization of the exercise brings the advantage of intrinsic

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Fig. 1. a) The developed immersive VR scenario with haptic feedback b) the light haptic thimble. c) and d) drawing sequence of the virtual exercise

parametrization, adaptability and repeatability of the exercises. Moreover, the gaming scenario improves active mental engagement of the user, which is critical in neurorehabilitation to promote brain plasticity [4]. On the other hand, only few studies introduced the sense of touch in the virtual setting [1]: whereas most of virtual system include only visual and audio sensory feedback, sense of touch is relevant in tasks involving manipulation, such as task-oriented upper-limb rehabilitation exercises. Although a rich variety of wearable haptic devices has been proposed in literature [5], introducing haptic feedback is challenging, and results usually in a compromise between different features: richness and intensity of the feedback versus lightweight and compactness of the devices in the shape of thimbles or gloves.

In this work, we present an innovative solution developed within project TELOS (<https://telos-project.eu/>) targeted at

upper limb rehabilitation of children with cerebral palsy in immersive virtual reality. In particular we took care to introduce the haptic feedback as a useful source of sensory information for the proposed task, considering at the same time the strict constraints for the haptic wearable devices to comply with patient’s comfort, residual motor abilities, and with the embedded tracking features of the latest VR technologies.

II. METHODS

A. The Virtual Exercise

The virtual scenario implements a typical rehabilitation task in the shape of a serious game. It consists of a path tracking exercise, involving upper limb motor synergies and visuo-motor coordination. The patient (children with CP) is immersed in the role of a wizard apprentice, and is required to precisely draw magic symbols in order to cast powerful spells. If the trajectory matches the reference symbol with a given precision, a spell is generated (Figure 1 c) and d). Regarding evaluation metrics of the patient’s outcome, important parameters are the precision of the executed trajectory and its smoothness: constant velocities are preferred with respect to higher accelerations and peaks.

B. Haptic rendering

We designed haptic feedback in order to be informative of the traveling velocity, hence helping the patient to perform the desired smooth movement. The idea is to provide a texture feeling while drawing the symbol, modulated on two degrees of freedom: the first dof modulates the rate of coarse texture transients, being informative of the absolute velocity of the finger. The second dof modulates the type of texture, changing it when the traveling velocity is close to a given velocity reference. In order to obtain the above signal modulation, two auto-regressive (AR) models are computed at the same time, each one synthesizing a different texture as presented in [2]. The input of the two AR is the same, and it is constituted by a train of pulsed gaussian noise with rate proportional to the traveling velocity. The output of the two ARs is mixed with a coefficient proportional to the velocity error (with respect to the given reference).

C. The Light Haptic Thimble

To render the above haptic signals, a light and thin haptic thimble has been developed with design targeted at lightweight, compact size and wearability. Key points in the design are the rendering high frequency components and fast transients of the haptic feedback, while eliminating static and slow force components in order to reduce actuator’s size. A miniaturized custom-made electromagnetic voice coil (outer diameter 12 mm, output force 0.4 N) was implemented to achieve high quality signals, and embedded in 3D printed, soft resin structure to maximize wearability (Cross section of the device shown in Figure 1b). A peculiar feature of the device is that the moving part of the voice coil is a soft membrane in contact with the fingerpad (blue element in Figure 1b). Deformation of the soft surface is intended to increase perception

Fig. 2. Experimental results measured in healthy participants regarding velocity error in the path tracking serious game. Conditions varied for the enabled haptic or visual feedback

of the feedback by fingertip mechanoreceptors. Total mass of the device is just 7 g.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

A brief experimental session with healthy adults has been performed before integration in the clinical setting: eight adult participants (30.25 ± 5.04 years old, 2 females) have been enrolled: they performed the gaming exercise in immersive VR in two conditions: with haptic feedback enabled, or with visual feedback (a coloured box was shown changing colour depending on the finger velocity). Two reference velocities were used. Results are shown in Figure 2: it was found a significant difference between haptic ($JI=9.89 \pm 3.74$) and visual ($JI=13.86 \pm 2.80$) feedback in the case of a slow speed ($p = .036$, $\chi^2 = 4.410$). It suggests the sensory feedback provided by the proposed haptic feedback was informative of the task execution and improved performance of the subject. More important, the whole haptic system resulted compatible with the rest of the VR system, in particular regarding hand tracking, and the final performance suggest it did not impact dexterity of the user. This compliance is relevant for introduction of such VR solutions in the final clinical rehabilitation settings.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bortone, I., Barsotti, M., Leonardis, D., Crecchi, A., Tozzini, A., Bonfiglio, L., Frisoli, A.: Immersive virtual environments and wearable haptic devices in rehabilitation of children with neuromotor impairments: a single-blind randomized controlled crossover pilot study. *Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation* **17**(1), 1–14 (2020)
- [2] Culbertson, H., Lopez Delgado, J.J., Kuchenbecker, K.J.: The penn haptic texture toolkit for modeling, rendering, and evaluating haptic virtual textures (2014)
- [3] Deutsch, J., McCoy, S.W.: Virtual reality and serious games in neurorehabilitation of children and adults: prevention, plasticity and participation. *Pediatric physical therapy: the official publication of the Section on Pediatrics of the American Physical Therapy Association* **29**(Suppl 3 IV STEP 2016 CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS), S23 (2017)
- [4] King, M., Regenbrecht, H., Hoermann, S., Heinrich, C., Hale, L.: Engaging stroke survivors with virtual neurorehabilitation technology. In: *Virtual Reality in Health and Rehabilitation*, pp. 103–116. CRC Press (2020)
- [5] Pacchierotti, C., Sinclair, S., Solazzi, M., Frisoli, A., Hayward, V., Prattichizzo, D.: Wearable haptic systems for the fingertip and the hand: taxonomy, review, and perspectives. *IEEE transactions on haptics* **10**(4), 580–600 (2017)